

An inter-laboratory comparison between 13 international laboratories for eight components relevant for hydrogen fuel quality assessment

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ABSTRACT

The quality of the hydrogen delivered by refuelling stations is critical for end-users and society. The purity of the hydrogen dispensed at hydrogen refuelling points should comply with the technical specifications included in the ISO 14687:2019 and EN 17124:2022 standards. Once laboratories have set up methods, they need to verify their performances, for example through participation in interlaboratory comparisons. Due to the challenge associated with the production of stable reference materials and transport of these which are produced in hydrogen at high pressure (>10 bar), interlaboratory comparisons have been organized in different steps, with increasing extent.

This study describes an inter-laboratory comparison exercise for hydrogen fuel involving a large number of participants (13 laboratories), completed in less than a year and included eight key contaminants of hydrogen fuel at level close to the ISO14687 threshold. These compounds were selected based on their high probability of occurrence or because they have been found in hydrogen fuel samples. For the results of the intercomparison, it appeared that fully complying with ISO 21087:2019 is still challenging for many participants and highlighted the importance of organising these types of exercises. Many laboratories performed corrective actions based on their results, which in turn significantly improved their performances.

1. Introduction

Fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) are one of the most efficient options for decarbonizing long-distance and heavy-duty vehicles [1]. They produce their electricity through a chemical reaction between hydrogen and oxygen in a fuel cell. FCEVs are emission free. However, FCEVs require extremely pure hydrogen. Hydrogen quality is vital for the performance and lifetime of hydrogen fuel cells, as even trace level contamination (e.g., carbon monoxide, hydrogen sulphide) may reduce the lifetime of the layers of catalyst added on both sides of the membrane. Even the polymer electrolyte membrane at the heart of the fuel cell can be damaged by some impurities such as ammonia. This catalyst is very sensitive to impurities, and it can be destroyed if the hydrogen fuel does not have an extremely high purity. Some contaminants (e.g., water) may have a detrimental impact on the hardware of fuel cell electrical vehicles. Therefore, ensuring the quality of the hydrogen delivered by the refuelling station is safety critical for end-users and society. The purity of the hydrogen dispensed at hydrogen refuelling

points should comply with the technical specifications included in the ISO 14687:2019 [2] and EN 17124:2022 [3] standards. These standards set maximum thresholds for 13 gaseous species that need to be quantified in hydrogen, including 3 total species (halogenated, hydrocarbons and sulphur). Performing these measurements is recognized as challenging [4].

To overcome this challenge, several European laboratories are developing the capability to measure the contaminants specified in these standards. These developments were undertaken in European projects (i. e., EMPIR project 16ENG01 MetroHyVe [5], Horizon 2020 project HYDRAITE [6]) or businesses and commercial incentives. In recent years, the number of laboratories which offer services to establish the purity of hydrogen has grown quickly. These laboratories need to prove their compliance to ISO 21087:2019 [7] which sets uncertainty thresholds and validation procedure to be met (i.e., relative measurement uncertainty < 20 %). Once laboratories have set up methods, they need to verify their accuracy.

Interlaboratory comparisons (ILC) [8] are an essential exercise for

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laboratories. They have two goals: 1) to check the ability of laboratories to deliver accurate results to their customers (usually termed 'proficiency testing') or, 2) to find out whether a given analytical method performs well and is fit for its intended purposes (usually termed 'collaborative method validation study'). Moreover, the participation to reviewed and approved scientific comparisons can be used to support the approval of Calibration and Measurement Capabilities. Through the framework of the International Committee for Weights and Measures Mutual Recognition Arrangement (CIPM MRA), National Metrology Institutes demonstrate the international equivalence of their measurement standards and the calibration and measurement certificates they issue. Several criteria are needed: (a) the results of a set of key comparisons carried out using specified procedures which lead to a quantitative measure of the degree of equivalence of national measurement standards; (b) the operation by each National Metrology Institute (NMI) of a suitable way of assuring quality; and (c) successful participation by each NMI in appropriate supplementary comparisons [9]. However, organizing ILC for hydrogen fuel quality is challenging due to the difficulty to produce the measurement standards specially at amount fraction level close to the threshold in the standards. Another challenge is the transport of these standards produced in hydrogen at high pressure (>10 bar) due to the nature of hydrogen itself. ILCs have therefore been organized in different steps, with increasing extent.

The first inter-laboratory comparison led by EURAMET (EURAMET 1220) showed that several NMIs and analytical laboratories have good agreement on measurement of carbon monoxide and hydrogen sulphide in hydrogen [10]. However, the amount fraction chosen for carbon monoxide and hydrogen sulphide were significantly higher than the hydrogen fuel threshold (250 times higher than the ISO 14687:2019 threshold). The finalization of the ILC took more than 2 years as the cylinder was transported between laboratory for analysis (2–3 months in each participating laboratory). Lowering the amount fraction in the next ILC was then required to gather evidence of measurement reliability at amount fraction coherent with hydrogen fuel threshold. In 16ENG01 MetroHyVe [5] an inter-laboratory comparison was organized in 2019 for four contaminants out of the 13 regulated in ISO 14687:2019. Nitrogen, water, and carbon monoxide amount fractions were chosen close to the standards thresholds whereas hydrogen sulphide amount fraction was only ten times higher than ISO 14687:2019 threshold. The results for some laboratories were satisfactory however, several participants needed to improve their performance. However, this study was performed at an amount fraction level for H₂S 250 times higher than the ISO 14687:2019 threshold. Moreover, the study only covered four contaminants out of 13. The challenges associated with the inclusion of more contaminants in ILC exercises were related to the stability of the contaminants in gas cylinder for a sufficient period of time to allow transport of the cylinder to the participants without impacting the amount fraction (i.e., instability) and knowledge of contaminants behavior in multicomponent mixture in hydrogen matrix. A recent study by Morris *et al.* [11] highlighted the feasibility to stabilize multicomponent mixture in hydrogen matrix. However, despite these recent advancements, extensive studies on multicomponent mixture stability are still lacking in various cylinder types to support an ILC exercise including the 13 species from ISO 14687:2019.

The purpose of this paper is to present a new and more extensive inter-laboratory comparison including eight contaminants out of 13. This study was performed during the project 19ENG04 MetroHyVe2. And included nitrogen (N₂), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), propane (C₃H₈), oxygen (O₂), water (H₂O), tetrachlorohexafluorobutane (C₄Cl₄F₆) and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) or carbonyl sulphide (COS) all in one cylinder. These compounds were selected based on their high probability of occurrence or because they have been found in hydrogen fuel samples. The number of participants that signed up for this ILC was 13, nine in Europe, three in Asia and one in USA. Each participant received an independent cylinder to ensure short duration of the exercise and limited transportation.

1.1. Selection of compounds for the ILC

The aim of ILCs is to allow laboratories to demonstrate that they perform reliable measurements and, as long as a study on the 13 compounds is too challenging, should focus on the most critical compounds. The characterization as most critical contaminants was based on their probability of occurrence which are defined as frequent, rare, very rare or unlikely [12] depending on the hydrogen production method. Nitrogen (frequent) and carbon monoxide (frequent) were selected for their relevance for steam methane reforming production processes while oxygen (rare), water (rare) and carbon dioxide (very rare) were selected for their relevance to electrolysis processes. As total hydrocarbons are often considered as an indicator for compressor issues, propane was added to the compounds previously mentioned. Total sulphur which impacts on fuel cells is critical even at low amount fractions was also selected. Moreover, the previous ILC were conducted at significant higher levels than the threshold (4 nmol/mol) so lowering the amount fraction of sulphur in this ILC was an important goal. Finally, "halogenated compounds" were also considered especially as tetrachlorohexafluorobutane (C₄Cl₄F₆) has been found in several hydrogen fuel samples [13].

2. Measurement standards

2.1. Gas mixtures preparation

A gas cylinder (10 L water volume, valve DIN 477 No.1) per participant was prepared by NPL in high-pressure cylinders (SGS, Luxfer, UK). All gas cylinders were prepared gravimetrically by dilution of NPL Primary Reference Materials (PRMs) in high purity hydrogen (99.9999 %, BIP+, Air Products, US) according to ISO 6142-1 [14]. All NPL PRMs used for the preparation were initially prepared gravimetrically from pure compounds in hydrogen matrix and certified by NPL according to ISO 6142-1 [14]. The transfer of gas from the parent cylinder was done using a well purged gas transfer line. The gas transfer line used was a 1/16" (Thames Restek, UK) treated tubing with Swagelok® connections with a minimum-dead-volume (MDV) connection (developed by NPL) at each end to connect to the cylinder. All components used were treated with Silconert® passivation (Thames Restek, UK). Purging was done via cyclic pressure purging a minimum of six times at each end of the filling line (the line was pressurised with filling gas then depressurised to displace residual air from the line). The cylinder used to prepare each sample was weighed against a tare cylinder (of equal size and shape) on a top pan electronic balance of type XPE26003LC (Mettler Toledo, US) using an automated weighing facility (KRIS, SK). The sample cylinders were weighed once they had been evacuated (before gas addition) and again after each addition. The mass of the PRM transferred was calculated using the mass difference between the cylinder before and after gas transfer [15]. The cylinders were rolled for 2 h to homogenise the gas mixture after the preparation.

The nominal composition of the mixtures in this comparison are within the ranges presented in Table 1. The nominal amount fractions were not provided to the participants, only a large range was communicated in order to allow to check method applicability (i.e., potential interference, working range).

The pressure was at least 60 bar in each cylinder. After measurement, the cylinders were requested to be returned to NPL for re-analysis.

During the preparation of the cylinders for the intercomparison, a large variation of behaviours for H₂S in the cylinders was observed with sometimes a significant decay. The variability between cylinders was assumed to be related to different surface reactivity from cylinder to cylinder. While H₂S is the most reactive sulphur compounds, an alternative and less reactive sulphur compound, COS was proposed. In order to not significantly delay the intercomparison, H₂S was replaced by COS (at the same levels as proposed in the protocol) for all participants except one as they didn't have the capability to measure COS.

Table 1

Nominal ranges of amount fraction communicated to participants and range of the reference materials provided to the participants.

Cylinder	unit	Amount fraction informed to participants	Nominal amount fraction range (min–max)
N ₂	μmol/mol	150–600	299—325
CO	μmol/mol	0.1–0.4	0.201 – 0.216
CO ₂	μmol/mol	1–4	2.183—2.377
C ₃ H ₈	μmol/mol	0.3—1.3	0.746 – 0.813
O ₂	μmol/mol	2.5—10	5.06 – 5.45
H ₂ O	μmol/mol	2.5—10	4.52 – 4.96
C ₄ Cl ₄ F ₆	μmol/mol	0.025 – 0.1	0.0457 – 0.0502
H ₂ S/ COS	μmol/mol	0.003 – 0.0015	0.0074 – 0.0084

2.2. Attribution of reference values

A reference value and associated uncertainty was established for the amount fraction of each of the component in each cylinder using accredited or validated analytical methods. The reference values and uncertainties used for the performance rating of the participants' results are given in annex B.

The sulphur amount fraction (COS and H₂S) was measured on a gas chromatograph coupled with a sulphur chemiluminescence detector (GC-SCD) (Agilent, UK). The method used a HP-1 column (60 m x 0.530 mm) with helium carrier. The sample loop size used for injection was 5 ml.

O₂ was analysed by gas chromatography (Agilent with pulsed discharge helium ionization detector (PDHID, VICI) using helium as a carrier gas. The GC/PDHID sampling loop was 1 ml. The sample was transferred onto capillary column molecular sieve 5A plot (30 m x 0.53 mm x 50 μm) and a second capillary column molecular sieve 5A plot (50 m x 0.53 mm x 50 μm). The GC oven was set at 30 degrees Celsius.

H₂O was measured using quartz crystal microbalance, QMA401 (Michell, US). Gases are sampled directly from the gas cylinder to the analyser, a valve was used to restrict the flow to 0.333 L/min for the QMA.

CO and CO₂ were measured with a gas chromatograph (Peak Laboratories, US) coupled with a flame ionization detector (GC/FID) with a methanizer. The method used a Hayesep D column (4.7 cm x 3.81 cm) with nitrogen carrier. The analysis of CO was realised with the column held at a temperature of 30 °C. The analysis of CO₂ was realised with the column held at a temperature of 65 °C. The loop size used for sample injection was 5 ml.

N₂ was measured using gas chromatograph with a thermal conductivity detector (GC-TCD) (Agilent Technologies, UK). The method used a HP-PLOT Q PT 15 m x 0.53 mm x 40 μm column, a HP-PLOT Molecular sieve 30 m x 0.53 mm x 50 μm column, and a section of fused silica tubing (diameter: 0.25 mm, length 1.5 m) with helium as carrier gas. The loop size used for sample injection was 2 ml.

C₃H₈ was measured using a GC-FID (Agilent, UK). The method used a DB 624 column (75 m x 0.535 mm OD with film thickness 3 μm) with helium carrier.

C₄Cl₄F₆ was analysed using selected ion flow tube – mass spectrometry (SIFT-MS), Voice 200 Ultra (Syft, NZ). The reagent ion used was O₂⁺ and the reaction product measured was at *m/z* 182 atomic mass unit (amu) (CF₃CHCl₂.H₃O⁺).

The reference value was established against a reference value (NPL primary reference material or a dynamically generated reference gas). All analytical instruments were calibrated using NPL gravimetric gas standards in hydrogen matrix gas. Gravimetric standards and/or

dynamic standards (prepared by dilution using mass flow controller system (Bronkhorst, NL)) were used to generate calibration curves in the range needed to cover the ISO 14687 threshold and the measured values (as long as it is above the limit of detection). The data was scrutinised however no result was discarded without a technical reason.

2.3. Analytical techniques used by the participants

The analytical techniques used by the participants for each component is shown in Table 2. From this table, it can be concluded that each laboratory requires at least four and up to eight different analytical methods to cover the eight components included in this ILC. It can also be seen that a variety of methods are used for each component, many of these methods are based on gas chromatography with different detectors: thermal conductivity detector (TCD), flame ionization detector (FID), pulse discharge helium ionization detector (PDHID), plasma emission detector (PED), flame photometric detector (FPD), sulphur chemiluminescence detector (SCD), mass spectrometry (MS), infrared spectroscopy as optical feedback, cavity enhanced adsorption spectroscopy (OFCEAS), fourier transform infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR) or spectrometry as ion–molecule reaction mass spectrometry (IMR-MS). Even component-specific methods have been selected (electrochemical sensor or cell, dew point hygrometer, QMA) by participants.

The large spectrum of techniques used in the ILC is interesting as it may allow to determine if there is technique variance or bias.

2.4. Data treatment and evaluation

To safeguard the anonymity of the participants, laboratory codes were used for identification. Some participants could not measure all components present in the mixture they received. Most of the participants reported measurement uncertainties for those requested amount fractions of the components they measured.

2.5. No data were excluded due to outliers or variance discrepancies

The results of the participants have been evaluated by means of zeta-scores using methods from ISO 13528:2022 [16] where the interpretation of the zeta-score is the following: $|\zeta| \leq 2$ is considered as a satisfactory result, $2 < |\zeta| \leq 3$ is considered as a questionable result and $|\zeta| > 3$ is considered as an unsatisfactory result. Zeta-scores (standardized measure of performance, calculated using the participant result, assigned value and the combined standard uncertainties for the result and the assigned value) are a measure for the relative distance from the reference value and help to evaluate a participant's ability to provide results close to the assigned value within their claimed uncertainty. They are calculated according to equation (1):

$$\zeta_i = \frac{x_i - x_{pt}}{\sqrt{u^2(x_i) + u^2(x_{pt})}} \quad (1)$$

3. x_i Represents the result (or the average of the replicates) reported by participant i

x_{pt} represents the assigned value in the reference laboratory.
 $u(x_{pt})$ is the standard uncertainty of the assigned value.
 $u(x_i)$ is the participant's own estimate of the standard uncertainty of its result.
 x_i

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Result of interlaboratory comparison

The overview of the zeta-scores obtained by the participants is shown in Table 3 where a color code is used to ease the interpretation of the results. The results are also provided graphically in supplementary

Table 2
Summary of analytical techniques used by the participants.

Lab code	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	C ₃ H ₈	O ₂	H ₂ O	C ₄ Cl ₄ F ₆	H ₂ S/COS
L01	GC-PDHID	FTIR	GC-FID	GC-FID	Electrochemical Sensor	CRDS	GC-MS	GC-PFPD
L02	GC-PDHID	GC-PDHID	GC-TCD	GC-TCD	GC-PDHID	CRDS	GC-MS	GC-SCD
L03	GC-TCD	GC-FID (MTN)	GC-FID (MTN)	GC-FID	Electrochemical Oxygen Meter	Dew point Hygrometer	/	Cryogenic-GC-SCD
L04	GC-PED	GC-PED	GC-PED	GC-FID	Portable trace oxygen analyser	Portable dew point analyser	GC-PED	GC-PED
L05	GC-TCD	GC-FID (MTN)	GC-FID (MTN)	GC-FID	GC-HPID	CRDS	TD-GC-MS	GC-FPD
L06	GC-PDHID	GC-PDHID	GC-PDHID	GC-FID	Electrochemical cell	CRDS	GC-ECD	GC-SCD
L07	μGC-TCD	OFCEAS	OFCEAS	GC-FID	OFCEAS	OFCEAS	TD-GC-XSD	TD-GC-PFPD
L08	GC-PED	GC-PED	IMR-MS	GC-PED	GC-PED	QMA	/	GC-SCD (with pre-concentrator)
L09	GC-PDHID	OFCEAS	GC-FID	GC-FID	GC-PDHID	OFCEAS	GC-PDECD	GC-FPD
L10	GC-TCD	/	GC-TCD	/	GC-TCD	/	/	*
L11	GC-TCD	GC-FID (MTN)	GC-PDHID	GC-FID	GC-PDHID	CRDS	TD-GC-MS	GC-SCD
L12	GC-PED	GC-PED	GC-PED	GC-FID	GC-PED	FTIR-OFCEAS	/	GC-PED
L13	EIS	FTIR	FTIR	IMR-MS	IMR-MS	FTIR	IMR-MS	IMR-MS

GC: Gas chromatography; PDHID: pulse discharge helium ionisation detector; FTIR: Fourier transformed infra-red spectroscopy; FID: flame ionisation detector; CRDS: cavity ringdown spectroscopy; PFPD: pulsed flame photometric detector; TCD: thermal conductivity detector; MS: mass spectrometry; SCD: sulphur chemiluminescence detector; MTN: methanizer; PED: plasma emission detector; TD: thermos-desorption; ECD: electron capture detector; OFCEAS: optical feedback cavity enhanced adsorption spectroscopy; XSD: halogen specific detector; IMR-MS: ion-molecule reaction mass spectrometry; QMA: quartz microbalance analyser; EIS: electron impact spectrometry, HPID: He Plasma Ionization Detector, *not communicated.

Table 3
Overview of the zeta-scores. The satisfactory zeta-score are shown in green, questionable zeta-score in orange and unsatisfactory zeta-score in red.

Lab code	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	C ₃ H ₈	O ₂	H ₂ O	C ₄ Cl ₄ F ₆	H ₂ S/COS
L01	-7.35	-7.86	-2.41	2.96	-13.15	4.92		-6.94
L02	-1.42	-0.67	-2.08	8.29	0.43	1.12	118,086	8.76
L03	5.76	-1.13	1.97	-3.34	-2.33	8.06		-4.88
L04	5.98	0.60	-1.68	-0.86	9.58	-2.23	-6.91	
L05	-0.02	0.99	0.18	1.52	7.02	-0.15	-1.75	-1.64
L06	0.39	-8.43	1.13	0.11	-0.29	1.33	1.94	4.41
L07	0.68	-4.18	0.71	2.25	-81.21	3.12		-4.79
L08	-2.05	2.79	14.15	-6.81		-3.60		-0.39
L09	-6.74	-2.35	-0.29	0.78	-0.03	1.14		-1.63
L10	-5.57		1.90		-1.03			-11.28
L11	-0.20	-0.02	0.42	-0.63	-0.24	0.56	0.44	-0.31
L12	-1.78	-1.90	-0.44	-1.97	1.80	11.53		-0.79
L13	0.36	2.56	2.90	2.72	2.17	1.20	-1.43	-1.04

materials for all compounds. The satisfactory zeta-score are shown in green, questionable zeta-score in orange and unsatisfactory zeta-score in red. The performance of the laboratories was relatively good with more than 58 % of the laboratories achieving satisfactory or questionable results on all the compounds tested.

The ILC results were presented graphically from the lower to the higher zeta score to give a simpler overview of the overall performance which is useful to identify challenges for the laboratory or for the organiser.

4.2. Example of good performance

The results of the ILC were good for most laboratories for CO₂ and propane. Fig. 1 presents visually an example where most of the laboratory were within a zeta score of 3.

Such results are positive for the ILC organiser and for the laboratory. It provides trust and reliability in the measurements realised by the participants.

4.3. Example of low performance

Low performance in ILC may be related to several factors such as the complexity of the analysis or the ability to measure. It helps identifying challenging measurement requiring further research and development effort for analytical methods, as well issues with standard and calibrant such as lack of availability.

The measurement of the halogenated compounds (here tetrachlorohexafluorobutane) and sulphur were good examples of challenging measurements as show in Fig. 2.

The results for sulphur amount fraction highlighted the challenge of this measurement as less than 50 % of the laboratories reported satisfactory results. The measurement was the first interlaboratory comparison at nmol/mol of sulphur. Therefore, most laboratories had never been able to perform external benchmarking. Secondly, it was the first realization of reference materials at such low amount fraction in an ILC. Despite the low performance, it can be seen a step in the right direction and an opportunity to progress and address measurement challenges identified through this external benchmarking.

Fig. 1. Overview of the zeta-scores in increasing order for carbon dioxide and propane.

The results of the ILC for tetrachlorohexafluorobutane was not satisfactory due to laboratories not able to measure specifically this compound (see Fig. 2). The lack of capability was also related to the lack of availability of the calibration gas or calibration materials.

The number of laboratories showing unsatisfactory results was highest for sulphur components, nitrogen and water. These compounds are critical for hydrogen fuel quality. It is critical to identify these measurement issues early in the technology deployment. Further work may be required to support laboratories to improve their performance (i.

e., corrective actions or new analytical methods).

4.3.1. Impact of analytical methods on performance

The results were scrutinized based on the different analytical methods used by the participants to determine if a specific technique may lead to biased results. This evaluation was limited in some case by the small number of laboratories using some of the techniques (i.e., IMR-MS). However, no significant differences were observed between techniques. Even if the study showed that the techniques used by participant

Fig. 2. Overview of the zeta-scores in increasing order for tetrachlorohexafluorobutane and sulphur.

were not the source of unsatisfactory results, further studies including a larger number of laboratories per technique would support a finer evaluation of potential variance due to techniques.

4.3.2. Impact of the ILC and corrective actions

Following the reporting of the performance to the participants, several participants investigated their results and prepared corrective actions (CA). Some of these participants provided revised results which were used to recalculate their zeta-score after the CA. The laboratory that realized CAs reported better results after. Even if the laboratory were aware of the assigned value by the time of the CAs, they provided technical explanations to support the changes realized (i.e., issue with calibration gases stability, human errors, instability of the analyser, cross-interferences).

The importance of CAs on the laboratories' performances and on the ILC exercise itself is demonstrated by the improvements of the results (see Tables 3 and 4). The lab-02 and Lab-06 got fully satisfactory results after CAs, identifying and improving thanks to the results of the exercise.

4.3.3. Perspective and future challenges for hydrogen purity assessment

The lack of reliable and stable gas calibrants was reported as a common issue by several participants specifically for sulphur components, for C₄Cl₄F₆ but even for CO. The lack of standard impacted the ability of the participants to perform the measurement or to determine the actual amount fraction and uncertainty. A recent report published as part of activity A2.1.1 [17] of MetroHyVe2 already discussed this aspect. This report outlined a number of calibrants that were of interest for the industry as for example a multi-component calibrant containing methane, oxygen, helium, nitrogen, argon, carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide at amount fractions corresponding to their respective EN17124:2022 and ISO14687:2019 thresholds preferably in 10-liter cylinders. Binary calibrants for reactive species and specifically for formaldehyde and formic acid were also highly required. Among the total species, development of calibrants for halogenated components were a priority for the laboratories who answered a survey on this topic.

Another common challenge reported was related to measurement uncertainty. As the measurement uncertainty of the participant is included in the determination of the zeta score, underestimation of the uncertainty may lead to poor performance. Many of the CAs were related to the measurement uncertainties provided by the participants. Those were either not provided with the results and calculated afterwards, or incorrect values were reported. One laboratory reported the smallest uncertainty for all the compounds measured. Compared to the other laboratories' performance and reported uncertainties, this laboratory may have underestimated its measurement uncertainty (i.e., assigned relative standard deviation as uncertainty). A recommendation to this laboratory would be to review their measurement uncertainties calculation as a change may significantly improve their zeta score and

provide a more realistic uncertainty on their measurements.

Some of the methods were time-consuming and required a large volume of the measurement standards for only one measurement, which prevented the laboratories to perform enough replicates. The ILC exercises tend to select the volume of gas to limit the cylinder transport duration and complexity (i.e., customs, air cargo transport). Therefore, the ILC trend will be on minimizing this volume in the future. There is a need to improve these methods to reduce time and volume of gas required while maintaining accuracy of the results.

Finally, instrument malfunction together with delay to identify and solved the issues and reporting mistakes were other reasons explaining unsatisfactory results, principally errors of units. The instruction on how to report sulphur components, halogens and hydrocarbons components amount fractions were not enough clear for some participants.

5. Conclusion

This study describes the most advanced inter-laboratory comparison exercise for hydrogen fuel so far based on the number of participants, number and amount fraction of contaminants and duration. It involved a large number of participants (13 laboratories), completed in less than a year and included eight key contaminants of hydrogen fuel at level close to the ISO14687 threshold.

The outcomes of the intercomparison highlighted a number of key points.

The lack of commercial and stable calibrants has impacted in some cases, the ability of participants to provide satisfactory results. This should prompt the gas calibrant industry to develop a platform of discussion with analytical laboratories for hydrogen fuel quality in order to share issues and requirements with the ultimate goal to develop reliable and well-adapted calibrants.

Instrument or methods issues were other challenges encountered by participants. As analysis of hydrogen is a new application for gas analyser manufacturers, these feedbacks can be used to improve some performances of instrument such as the response time or robustness.

For the results of the intercomparison, it appears clearly that fully complying with ISO 21087:2019 is very challenging for many participants. The biggest challenge is often on the measurement uncertainties where large variations were observed between participants. Sometimes, measurement uncertainties stated were too stringent, leading to unsatisfactory results.

This ILC highlighted the overall good performance of laboratory on hydrogen fuel quality but also the importance to organize these types of exercise. Many laboratories performed CAs based on their results, which in turn significantly improved their performances. Improvement of results is still needed and therefore regular ILC is a key element to support the progress of analytical laboratories.

Table 4
Overview of the zeta-scores after corrective actions.

Lab code	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	C ₃ H ₈	O ₂	H ₂ O	C ₄ Cl ₄ F ₆	H ₂ S/COS
L01	-7.35	-7.86	-2.41	2.96	-13.15	4.92		-6.94
L02	-1.42	-0.67	-1.72*	-1.86*	0.43	1.12	1.78*	-1.06*
L03	5.76	-1.13	1.97	-3.34	-2.33	8.06		-4.88
L04	5.98	0.60	-1.68	-0.86	9.58	-2.23	-6.91	
L05	-0.02	0.99	0.18	1.52	7.02	-0.15	-1.75	-1.64
L06	0.39	-0.48*	1.13	0.11	-0.29	1.33	1.94	0.34*
L07	0.68	-0.12*	-0.21*	2.25	-0.38*	3.12		-3.74*
L08	-2.05	2.79	14.15	-6.81		-3.60		-0.39
L09	-1.03*	-2.35	-0.29	0.78	-0.03	1.14		-1.63
L10	-5.57		1.90		-1.03			-11.28
L11	-0.20	-0.02	0.42	-0.63	-0.24	0.56	0.44	-0.31
L12	-1.78	-1.90	-0.44	-1.97	1.80	1.50*		-0.79
L13	0.36	2.56	2.90	2.72	2.17	1.20	-1.43	-1.04

*Results after implementation of CAs (in light green).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Karine Arrhenius: Writing – original draft. **Abigail Morris:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Mathew Hookham:** Data curation. **Niamh Moore:** Data curation. **Pierpaolo Modugno:** Data curation. **Thomas Bacquart:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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